

Field Averaging Techniques in Electromagnetic Problems

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Abstract—In this work we present two field averaging techniques for structured electromagnetic materials. One is concerned with 3D-periodic composite media, while the other one is concerned with 2D-periodic planar structures. In the first case, the field averaging is prescribed by the integral form of Maxwell’s equations and is carried out along the paths laying at the boundaries of the unit cell. In the second case, the integration regions are prescribed by the Generalized Sheet Transition Conditions. Both techniques are useful in homogenization of structured materials such as metamaterials and metasurfaces, for the extraction of their effective material parameters and surface susceptibilities, respectively.

I. INTRODUCTION

Homogenization of composite electromagnetic media for the extraction of their effective parameters has been a very popular research topic throughout the recent years, following the massive explosion of interest in metamaterials [1]–[11]. Accordingly, in the case of metasurfaces – the two-dimensional analog of metamaterials – the term *characterization* is utilized for the extraction of their effective surface susceptibilities [12]–[15]. Recently, two distinct homogenization techniques were proposed: The first one concerns the effective electromagnetic parameter retrieval of arbitrarily bianisotropic composite periodic media, which returns accurately fifteen effective electric, magnetic and magnetoelectric parameters [16]. The other one is about the characterization of general bianisotropic metasurface structures, which successfully extracts the corresponding effective surface susceptibility tensors [17]. Both methods utilize computational information obtained by the eigenmode analysis of the unit cell of each structure, combined with averaging of the field components of the modes supported by these structures.

In this work, we provide a presentation of the field averaging techniques in electromagnetic problems, focusing on the cases of 3D-periodic composite media and planar 2D-periodic structures. Beginning with the numerical treatment of periodic computational domains based on the Finite Element Method’s eigenvalue field-flux formulations, we obtain the dispersion diagrams and the field distributions of the modes supported by each periodic structure [18]–[22]. Subsequently,

we discuss the proposed field averaging technique for 3D-periodic metamaterials. There, we illustrate the alternative integration regions for every field variable, which are prescribed by the integral form of Maxwell’s equations and present the respective results. Then, we present the corresponding technique for a 2D-periodic metasurface. In this case, the proper integration regions are based on the Generalized Sheet Transition Conditions, the set of equations which connect the field quantities above and below an electromagnetically thin surface with its surface susceptibilities.

II. NUMERICAL TREATMENT OF EIGENVALUE ELECTROMAGNETIC PROBLEMS

In this section we describe the computational procedure for the acquisition of the solution of a periodic structure. For reasons that are thoroughly explained in [16], [17], we mention that it is required to acquire all four field variables at the same order of approximation (electric field, magnetic field, dielectric displacement and magnetic induction). To this end, we make use of the **e-b** Finite Element periodic formulation, along with its dual counterpart, the **h-d** formulation. A detailed derivation of these formulations is presented in [16], [22]. Here, we briefly describe the **e-b** formulation. We also note that all the computational tools were implemented in the Weak Form of Comsol MultiphysicsTM and verified in custom in-house codes in MatlabTM, returning identical results when solved for the same number of degrees of freedom. Throughout the work, the time-factor $\exp(j\omega t)$ is assumed and suppressed, with ω being the angular frequency and t being the time.

Beginning with the Bloch-Floquet theorem, we write the the electric field \mathbf{E} and the magnetic induction \mathbf{B} as the product of their periodic envelopes \mathbf{e} and \mathbf{b} , respectively, and an exponential factor as

$$\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{e}e^{-j\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{r}} \quad (1a)$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{b}e^{-j\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{r}}, \quad (1b)$$

where $\mathbf{k} = k\hat{\mathbf{k}}$ is the Bloch-Floquet wavevector of prescribed propagation direction $\hat{\mathbf{k}}$ (e.g. $\hat{\mathbf{k}} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}$) and $k = \beta - j\alpha$ is the

unknown complex propagation constant. If we substitute Eqs. (1) into Maxwell's curl equations in the frequency domain, the following modified Maxwell's equations are obtained in terms of the periodic field envelopes

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{e} - jk\hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{e} = -j\omega\mathbf{b} \quad (2a)$$

$$\nabla \times \bar{\bar{\mu}}_r^{-1} \mathbf{b} - jk\hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \bar{\bar{\mu}}_r^{-1} \mathbf{b} = j\omega\epsilon_0\mu_0\bar{\bar{\epsilon}}_r \mathbf{e}, \quad (2b)$$

where $\bar{\bar{\epsilon}}_r$ and $\bar{\bar{\mu}}_r$ are the 3×3 tensors of relative dielectric permittivity and relative magnetic permeability, respectively. The Galerkin formulation for this system of equations is feasible by taking the projection of the first equation with the test magnetic induction field \mathbf{b}' , the projection of the second equation with the test electric field \mathbf{e}' and integrating inside the volume V of the computational domain, enclosed by the surface S

$$\begin{aligned} \iiint_V \mathbf{b}' \cdot \nabla \times \mathbf{e} \, dV - jk \iiint_V \mathbf{b}' \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{e} \, dV \\ = -j\omega \iiint_V \mathbf{b}' \cdot \mathbf{b} \, dV \end{aligned} \quad (3a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \iiint_V \bar{\bar{\mu}}_r^{-1} \mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla \times \mathbf{e}' \, dV - jk \iiint_V \mathbf{e}' \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \bar{\bar{\mu}}_r^{-1} \mathbf{b} \, dV \\ = j\omega\epsilon_0\mu_0 \iiint_V \mathbf{e}' \cdot \bar{\bar{\epsilon}}_r \mathbf{e} \, dV + \iint_S (\mathbf{e}' \times \bar{\bar{\mu}}_r^{-1} \mathbf{b}) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}} \, dS, \end{aligned} \quad (3b)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ denotes the outward unitary vector normal to the boundary. Application of the appropriate boundary conditions and expansion of the electric field \mathbf{e} with tangentially continuous edge-based H -curl elements and magnetic flux density \mathbf{b} with normally continuous facet-based H -div elements, results in the linear eigenvalue problem

$$\begin{bmatrix} -j\omega\epsilon_0\mu_0 \mathbf{T}^{E'E} + \mathbf{T}_s^{E'E} & \mathbf{Q}^{E'B} - \mathbf{T}_s^{E'B} \\ \mathbf{Q}^{B'E} & j\omega \mathbf{T}^{B'B} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{E} \\ \mathbf{B} \end{bmatrix} = k \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -j\mathbf{P}^{E'B} \\ -j\mathbf{P}^{B'E} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{E} \\ \mathbf{B} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

where the submatrices are defined in [22]. We note that the solution of this matrix eigenvalue problem returns the eigenpairs (i.e., the complex propagation constant as eigenvalue k and the corresponding field distribution as eigenvector) for a given frequency. This way, numerical information is acquired all over the simulated frequency spectrum, both at passband and at bandgap regions.

The structures under consideration in this work are i) a 3D-periodic composite metamaterial medium consisting of edge-coupled split-ring resonators (EC-SRRs), with its unit cell illustrated in Fig. 1 and ii) a 2D-periodic metasurface consisting of the same type of resonators (Fig. 2 depicts its unit cell). In the first case, the computational domain is terminated at Periodic Boundary Conditions (PBC) at all three orthogonal axes, whereas for the metasurface, periodicity is imposed at x

Fig. 1. (a) Unit cell of the EC-SRR composite periodic medium. The resonators are arranged on a cubic lattice of an edge of $d = 8.8$ mm (b) Dimensions of the resonator (in mm): The metallic rings are made of copper, have a thickness of $17 \mu\text{m}$ and lay on air.

Fig. 2. (Left) Unit cell of the EC-SRR metasurface. The resonators are arranged on a tetragonal lattice (with an edge of $d = 7.5$ mm). Periodicity is imposed on xz and yz boundaries, whereas an Absorbing Boundary Condition terminates the xy boundaries of the computational domain. In-plane Bloch-Floquet wave incidence is illustrated along with the up and down integration volumes for the field averaging. (Right) Dimensions of the resonator (in mm): The metallic rings are made of copper and have a thickness of $17 \mu\text{m}$.

and y directions and the domain is terminated at the normal direction at an Absorbing Boundary Condition (ABC) of first order. The dispersion diagram for the composite medium, for the case of k_x propagation is illustrated in Fig. 3. The medium supports two kinds of modes, the lightline mode, where the electromagnetic field ignores the existence of the scatterers and propagates as in free space, and the SRR mode, through which the electromagnetic field interacts with the resonators and produces a hybrid type of wave. The distribution of the E_z , the electric field component normal to the resonator's plane, is shown in Fig. 4, at planes below and above the resonator. A sign change is observed on the distribution, which indicates the existence of surface charges, according to the boundary conditions for the dielectric displacement.

In the case of the metasurface structure, its dispersion diagram is illustrated in Fig. 5 for both cases of k_x and k_y incidence. There, it is obvious that both wave incidences return similar dispersion curves, with a bandgap between 8.1 and 8.5 GHz, whereas these results bear a significant resemblance to the dispersion curve of the 3D-case (at another frequency zone, due to the different resonator dimensions). Taking this into account, along with the associated supported mode distributions shown in Fig. 6, allows us to conclude that it is the surface mode with the same characteristics supported by both the metasurface and the metamaterial composite medium [17].

Fig. 3. Dispersion diagram of the EC-SRR composite periodic medium for k_x incidence: propagation constant β (rad/m) and attenuation constant α (Np/m). Propagating EC-SRR modes are plotted in blue, evanescent EC-SRR modes with large real part of the propagation constant in green and evanescent EC-SRR modes with small real part of the propagation constant in red. A frequency bandgap is observed between 5.3 and 6 GHz. Lightline modes are illustrated in black.

Fig. 4. Normal component of the electric field (E_z) (V/m) (a) above the resonator (b) below the resonator for the SRR mode of k_x incidence at $f = 4$ GHz for the composite periodic medium.

III. AVERAGING THE ELECTROMAGNETIC FIELD AT COMPOSITE STRUCTURES WITH 3D-PERIODICITY

Calculation of average electromagnetic fields is feasible when the behavior of a composite medium is investigated at frequency zones, where its effective, homogenized parameters are well-defined [16]: The guided wavelength is much larger than the largest dimension α of the unit cell ($\lambda_g \gg \alpha$) and there is no existence of higher order Bloch-Floquet modes. In this case, we require the substitution of the microscopic electromagnetic quantities from the numerical solution of a composite medium with macroscopic, average, unique values, which will account for the interaction of the electromagnetic field with the homogenized medium.

It is the Maxwell's curl equations in integral form that propose the appropriate means of averaging the microscopic field quantities: Projection of the tangentially continuous microscopic fields on line segments parallel to specific axes leads to the evaluation of average fields with tangential continuity. The most obvious options for the paths of integration in this case are the edges of the unit cell or its facet medians. For example, assuming a cubic unit cell of edge α , the average x -field component of the electric and magnetic field periodic envelopes may respectively be calculated as

Fig. 5. Dispersion diagrams of the EC-SRR metasurface for in-plane incidence k_x and k_y . Real part (left) and imaginary part (right) of the complex propagation constant $k = \beta - j\alpha$. Both incidences' dispersion curves asymptotically tend to the lightline for the upper branch, as it is analytically predicted [23] (utilization of a denser FEM mesh is expected to provide a better numerical approximation of the returned eigenpairs at higher simulated frequencies.)

Fig. 6. Normal component (E_z) above (left) and below (right) the resonator at 5 GHz for the case of k_x incidence at an EC-SRR metasurface.

$$\mathbf{e}_{\text{av}_x} = \frac{1}{\alpha} \int_{l=-\alpha/2}^{l=\alpha/2} \mathbf{e} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{x}} dl \quad (5a)$$

$$\mathbf{h}_{\text{av}_x} = \frac{1}{\alpha} \int_{l=-\alpha/2}^{l=\alpha/2} \mathbf{h} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{x}} dl. \quad (5b)$$

Following, projection of the microscopic normally continuous field components on the facets of the unit cell, leads to the evaluation of the average fields with normal continuity

$$\mathbf{d}_{\text{av}_x} = \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \iint_{S_x} \mathbf{d} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{x}} dS_x \quad (6a)$$

$$\mathbf{b}_{\text{av}_x} = \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \iint_{S_x} \mathbf{b} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{x}} dS_x, \quad (6b)$$

where S_x , S_y and S_z are the surfaces of the facets normal to x , y and z axes, respectively.

Furthermore, another equivalent choice for the averaging of field components could be the integration on a number of parallel line segments or cross sections: In a more rigorous mathematical sense, the limit of infinite parallel line integrations of a tangential vector component on a facet approaches its integral

Fig. 7. Average electric (a), (b), (c) and magnetic (d), (e), (f) field components corresponding to the lightline mode of k_x incidence for the EC-SRR composite periodic medium. Results returned from integration on face median are plotted in red, those returned from integration on the unit cell's edges are plotted in blue and facet integration is plotted in black (e.g. for x component: facet #1 and facet #2 correspond to xy master and slave facets, respectively, whereas facet #3 and facet #4 indicate xz master and slave facets, respectively).

on the surface of a facet, whereas the limit of infinite parallel facet integrations of a normal vector component approaches the volume integral over the volume of the computational domain. To this end, we proposed an alternative field averaging procedure where tangentially continuous \mathbf{e} and \mathbf{h} components are integrated on the corresponding facets (e.g. e_x on xy and xz boundaries) and normalize the integrals by the corresponding facet area ($S_i = \alpha^2$), whereas normally continuous components \mathbf{d} and \mathbf{b} are integrated on the whole volume of the unit cell and normalized by the volume ($V = \alpha^3$).

In Fig. 7 we illustrate the returned results from the described technique for the case of the lightline mode of k_x propagation. The dominant components are \mathbf{e}_{av_z} and \mathbf{h}_{av_y} , whereas the rest of the average field components are numerically zero. Consequently, the *average* field type for this mode may be characterized as a TEM wave, polarized as $(\mathbf{e}_{av_z}, \mathbf{h}_{av_y}, k_x)$. Fig. 8 depicts the field averaging results for the SRR mode of k_x incidence. The dominant electric field component is \mathbf{e}_{av_y} , with the other two components numerically zero. It is observed that the magnitude of \mathbf{e}_{av_y} exhibits a resonant behavior: it decreases for frequencies near resonance, whereas it increases at frequencies beyond the bandgap region. The dominant magnetic field component is \mathbf{h}_{av_z} , with qualitatively the same behavior as \mathbf{e}_{av_y} .

IV. FIELD AVERAGING TECHNIQUE FOR COMPOSITE STRUCTURES WITH 2D-PERIODICITY

We now turn our attention on the averaging of the field components in periodic metasurfaces, i.e., the composite structures with in-plane 2D-periodicity. In this case, as thoroughly described in [17], field averaging is prescribed by the Generalized Sheet Transition Conditions (GSTCs), the equations which relate the field components above and below a (meta)surface as follows

Fig. 8. Average electric (a), (b), (c) and magnetic (d), (e), (f) field components corresponding to the SRR mode of k_x incidence for the EC-SRR composite periodic medium. Legend described in the caption of Fig. 7.

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} \times (\mathbf{H}_+ - \mathbf{H}_-) = j\omega \mathbf{P}_{s,t} - \hat{\mathbf{n}} \times \nabla_t \mathbf{M}_{s,n} \quad (7a)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} \times (\mathbf{E}_+ - \mathbf{E}_-) = -j\omega \mu \mathbf{M}_{s,t} - \left(\frac{1}{\epsilon_0}\right) \hat{\mathbf{n}} \times \nabla_t \mathbf{P}_{s,n} \quad (7b)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot (\mathbf{D}_+ - \mathbf{D}_-) = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{P}_{s,t} \quad (7c)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot (\mathbf{B}_+ - \mathbf{B}_-) = \mu \nabla \cdot \mathbf{M}_{s,t}. \quad (7d)$$

Here, we denote the surface electric polarization density with \mathbf{P}_s , the surface magnetic polarization density with \mathbf{M}_s , the electric field above and below the metasurface with \mathbf{E}_+ , \mathbf{E}_- , respectively, the corresponding magnetic fields with \mathbf{H}_+ , \mathbf{H}_- , respectively, whereas the subscripts t and n denote the tangential and normal parts of the vectors, respectively, and $\mu = \mu_0 \mu_r$. For the case of a general bianisotropic metasurface, electric and magnetic surface polarization densities are connected through the electric, magnetic, electro-magnetic and magnetoelectric surface susceptibility tensors ($\overline{\overline{\chi}}_{ee}$, $\overline{\overline{\chi}}_{mm}$, $\overline{\overline{\chi}}_{em}$ and $\overline{\overline{\chi}}_{me}$), respectively, as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{P}_s \\ \frac{1}{c_0} \mathbf{M}_s \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \overline{\overline{\chi}}_{ee} & \overline{\overline{\chi}}_{em} \\ \overline{\overline{\chi}}_{me} & \overline{\overline{\chi}}_{mm} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_0 \overline{\mathbf{E}} \\ \frac{1}{c_0} \overline{\mathbf{H}} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (8)$$

where $\overline{\mathbf{E}} = (\mathbf{E}_+ + \mathbf{E}_-)/2$ and $\overline{\mathbf{H}} = (\mathbf{H}_+ + \mathbf{H}_-)/2$ are the mean electric and magnetic fields at the two sides of the metasurface, respectively. Combining Eqs. (7) and (8), the GSTCs for the general case of a bianisotropic metasurface may be written as

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} \times (\mathbf{H}_+ - \mathbf{H}_-) = j\omega \left[\epsilon_0 (\overline{\overline{\chi}}_{ee} \overline{\mathbf{E}})_t + \frac{1}{c_0} (\overline{\overline{\chi}}_{em} \overline{\mathbf{H}})_t \right] - \hat{\mathbf{n}} \times \nabla_t [(\overline{\overline{\chi}}_{mm} \overline{\mathbf{H}})_n + c_0 \epsilon_0 (\overline{\overline{\chi}}_{me} \overline{\mathbf{E}})_n] \quad (9a)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} \times (\mathbf{E}_+ - \mathbf{E}_-) = -j\omega \mu [(\overline{\overline{\chi}}_{mm} \overline{\mathbf{H}})_t + c_0 \epsilon_0 (\overline{\overline{\chi}}_{me} \overline{\mathbf{E}})_t] - \hat{\mathbf{n}} \times \nabla_t \left[\epsilon_0 (\overline{\overline{\chi}}_{ee} \overline{\mathbf{E}})_n + \frac{1}{c_0} (\overline{\overline{\chi}}_{em} \overline{\mathbf{H}})_n \right] \quad (9b)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot (\mathbf{D}_+ - \mathbf{D}_-) = -\nabla \cdot [\epsilon_0 (\overline{\overline{\chi}}_{ee} \overline{\mathbf{E}})_t + \frac{1}{c_0} (\overline{\overline{\chi}}_{em} \overline{\mathbf{H}})_t] \quad (9c)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot (\mathbf{B}_+ - \mathbf{B}_-) = \mu \nabla \cdot [(\overline{\overline{\chi}}_{mm} \overline{\mathbf{H}})_t + c_0 \epsilon_0 (\overline{\overline{\chi}}_{me} \overline{\mathbf{E}})_t]. \quad (9d)$$

A closer look at Eqs. (9) reveals that both the field components and the field derivatives are involved above and below the metasurface at directions tangential and normal to

Fig. 9. Average electric field (left) and average magnetic field (right) components above and below the metasurface for both in-plane incidences for an EC-SRR metasurface.

the metasurface. Therefore, it follows that the selection of any possible integration regions should be able to enclose all the required computational information on either side of the structure, including differentiation with respect to any direction. As thoroughly explained in [17], we propose that the field averaging in this case is done by integrating over the volumes of the unit cell above and below the metasurface. For example (see Fig. 2), the average x component of the electric field E_x^+ above the metasurface is calculated by integrating the field distribution E_x inside the volume V_{up} above the metasurface as

$$E_x^+ = \frac{1}{V_{up}} \iiint_{V_{up}} E_x dV_{up}. \quad (10)$$

It is obvious that the corresponding average component E_x^- is integrated inside the volume V_{down} below the metasurface and calculated through

$$E_x^- = \frac{1}{V_{down}} \iiint_{V_{down}} E_x dV_{down}. \quad (11)$$

The dominant, average electric and magnetic field components of the examined EC-SRR metasurface are illustrated in Fig. 9 for both in-plane incidence cases (k_x and k_y). It is found that there is a similar behavior of these components for both incidences (average E_y , H_z for k_x incidence and average E_x , H_z for k_y incidence, respectively). Comparison with the corresponding dominant field components for the 3D-periodic metamaterial in Section II leads to a conclusion that all the dominant field components coincide for both incidence cases and have a very similar behavior of their magnitudes around the resonant frequencies.

V. CONCLUSION

We have presented two distinct ways to average the electromagnetic field components in composite electromagnetic structures. Given the numerical solution of a problem and the acquisition of the microscopic field quantities all over the computational domain (the unit cell of a periodic structure), we have proposed the proper regions for the evaluation of the field

averages for the cases of 3D-periodic composite media (metamaterials) and 2D-periodic planar structures (metasurfaces). The presented techniques may be used as part of homogenization techniques for the extraction of effective parameters in metamaterials, and the characterization of metasurfaces through the extraction of their effective surface susceptibilities.

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